

Load Shedding Resilient Filterless Horseshoe Networks with Point-to-Multipoint Transceivers

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Abstract—While horseshoe filterless networks with point-to-multipoint (P2MP) transceivers offer a cost-effective solution with inherent survivability against single-link failures, certain scenarios may demand an even higher degree of network resilience. This is particularly true in regions with frequent power outages and/or where load shedding is enforced. Addressing this problem requires a careful design and trade-off between survivability and cost. This paper describes a multi-objective optimization framework based on Integer Linear Programming (ILP) that accurately models the problem and can be used to obtain solutions that prioritize one or the other metric. Moreover, the paper reports a study using a set of randomly generated horseshoe topologies that demonstrates how strategically placing amplifiers and unbalanced couplers can significantly enhance network resilience, while also keeping the minimum number of additional optical amplifiers required.

Index Terms—Coherent point-to-multipoint, availability, survivable networks, amplifier placement, load shedding.

I. INTRODUCTION

Metro-aggregation networks can benefit from adopting specific physical topologies and transmission technologies due to their relatively high-capacity links and tight survivability requirements. Common network topologies – used in this network segment – are horseshoe, and ring [1], [2]. Emerging coherent point-to-multipoint (P2MP) transceivers, enabled by digital subcarrier coherent multiplexing (DSCM) [3], offer a promising alternative to traditional coherent point-to-point (P2P) solutions for cost-effectively addressing hub-and-spoke traffic patterns present in metro-aggregation networks. This technology allows for the aggregation of multiple small traffic flows into a single high-capacity device at hub nodes, leading to significant improvements in key metrics such as cost, power consumption, and space utilization [4].

Filterless optical networks differ from traditional wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) networks by employing passive optical splitters and combiners and a limited number of fixed filters [5] instead of reconfigurable add/drop multiplexers (ROADM). Combining DSCM transmission with a filterless architecture can reduce to a minimum the utilization of active optical switches/filters and expensive and power-hungry electronic components – e.g., used for intermediate traffic flow

aggregation – leading to a solution that can offer simplified network management, significant cost savings, and reduced power consumption [6], [7]. It is noteworthy that this approach is most suitable when the amount of capacity needed is much less than the C-band spectrum [8].

Since perfect up-time is impossible, engineers use availability to quantify how reliably a system functions. Availability reflects the percentage of time a network link or a device is expected to be operational and can be estimated using historical data regarding failures and their corresponding repair times [9]. Optical networks can experience failure due to various factors, including fiber cuts, device malfunctions (e.g., amplifier or transponder failures), human errors, natural disasters, and special circumstances like electrical power outages. The key approach for increasing the availability is to incorporate redundancy [10]. This ensures that there are multiple independent connection links for data to travel. However, maintaining network survivability is more challenging in non-meshed filterless networks due to limited optical fiber links, and limited or no switching capabilities. Therefore, extra equipment such as wavelength blockers, blue and red filters [11] are often required. Although there is no one-size-fits-all solution, network operators must address their unique challenges in building and maintaining cost-effective protected network operations.

Most of the protection solutions are based on the fact that two failures at the same time are extremely unlikely [12]. However, scenarios with more than two simultaneous failures should not always be neglected. While single-link failures are well understood and recovery mechanisms are relatively fast (milliseconds to seconds), repairs can take hours or even days [13]. This extended window creates vulnerabilities to double-link/node failures, where a second link/node fails before the first is repaired. Moreover, when the network consists of many optical fiber links and nodes or when the failure rates are high, the probability of such events becomes non-negligible and topologies like horseshoe may fail to grant connectivity for all leaf nodes. It is important to consider that failures can affect links or nodes and their connected links (since a failed node inherently disconnects incoming and outgoing links) [14].

Electricity outages can easily undermine the performance

of networks and can be caused by power grid failure, natural disasters, or load shedding [15]. In this paper, we propose a design and optimization approach for a filterless horseshoe network that employs P2MP transceivers and is resistant to load shedding. To prevent entire power grids from collapsing, load shedding involves strategically cutting off power to certain areas and forcefully reducing demand to match limited supply. Load shedding ideally occurs on a set schedule that lasts a few hours (2-4 hours), but often the schedule changes with short notice or even without notice [16]. Certain backup power sources are deployed to keep equipment powered during load shedding while minimizing disruption, such as a combination of backup generators, battery banks, solar and other renewable energy sources, all deployed at a higher cost than grid power [17]. For instance, South Africa’s unreliable power grid forced operators to divert a substantial amount, around 12% of their 2023 CapEX, towards backup power investments. However, extra visible investments can make sites more vulnerable to thievery or vandalism to the surrounding community that does not have backup electricity during load shedding [18] leading to higher security costs. Therefore, network design and transmission technologies that enhance redundancy and availability for such a power-constrained environment are crucial.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section II introduces the details of our proposed architectural solution. In Section III, we present an Integer Linear Programming (ILP) optimization framework, detailing the input parameters, variables, and constraints specifically designed for the strategic or efficient deployment of optical amplifiers and couplers, while adhering to predefined practical design limitations. Finally, Section IV presents and discusses the results obtained.

II. ARCHITECTURAL SOLUTION

A horseshoe topology can inherently provide single-link and single-hub protection [1] due to redundancy in the hubs and the number of transceivers at the leaf nodes (similar to 1+1 protection [19]). The use of passive devices such as splitters/combiners instead of ROADMs significantly decreases the probability of node failures. However, in filterless networks, amplifiers are often needed to compensate for losses. Although erbium-doped fiber amplifiers (EDFAs) are highly reliable, their effectiveness in long-distance applications can be limited. This is particularly true for subsea cables, which can stretch for thousands of kilometers and require numerous amplifiers [20] and consequently, some type of redundancy in their power supply or laser sources is needed. Obviously, unreliable power sources can also hinder their availability.

Fig. 1 (a) shows the topology of a 5-leaf node filterless horseshoe based on a passive 2-by-2 coupler node architecture and the possible location of amplifiers. Amplifiers can be located before each leaf node for each direction, as booster or pre-amp at hub nodes or at add/drop ports of leaf nodes. Importantly, a power outage (deliberate or not) can affect the amplifiers at one or more leaf nodes. Notably, express amplifiers are more crucial than add/drop amplifiers because

they amplify signals directed to/generated at multiple leaf nodes. When a power outage disables an express amplifier, it essentially blocks all optical signals passing through it. A power outage at one of the hubs disables the horseshoe protection mechanism, and we do not consider this case (hubs should be protected against power outages, e.g., by using backup generators or batteries). In Fig. 1(a), we can observe two simultaneous failures: a power outage in leaf 2 and a fiber cut between leaf nodes 4 and 5. It is worth noting that unlike fiber cuts, which typically affect both directions, a downed express amplifier can virtually split a single fiber direction into two isolated segments. In the scenario depicted, leaf nodes 2, 3, and 4 lose connectivity with Hub 1 as well as Hub 2. It is important to keep in mind that each fiber carries one downstream and one upstream signal of each leaf node.

Similarly, Fig. 1(b) demonstrates the impact of power outages at leaf nodes 2 and 4. In this case, nodes 2, 3, and 4 are impacted and service is interrupted in all of them, while leaf nodes 1 and 5 still have successful downstream and upstream connections with Hub 1 and Hub 2, respectively. Note that the red and green circles represent unavailable and available downstream and upstream connections for each fiber.

As referred, compared to add/drop amplifiers, which are only required to amplify the locally added or dropped channels, express amplifiers have the task of amplifying multiple channels, making them a more critical point of failure. To improve horseshoe resilience, we consider deploying a reduced number of express amplifiers or eliminating them when possible, transitioning the express line to a fully passive operation. However, achieving this while maintaining the feasibility of all connections most likely requires a more intensive utilization of add/drop amplifiers. The distribution of express amplifiers also plays a crucial role in horseshoe network survivability. A horseshoe network with two express amplifiers in the same fiber or with two amplifiers in the same leaf node in different directions is still survivable (other than directly affected leaf nodes). However, having two express amplifiers at separate leaf nodes and different fiber directions creates a vulnerability for intermediate leaf nodes. Therefore, it is important to reduce the number of amplification sites to improve survivability instead of only express amplifiers.

III. OPTIMIZATION FRAMEWORK

We consider three goals in our proposed optimization framework for load shedding resilient filterless horseshoe networks:

- Number of amplification sites: this parameter presents the number of leaf nodes hosting at least one express amplifier and is a metric of load shedding vulnerability.
- Total number of amplifiers: this presents the total number of amplifiers including express, add/drop, and booster/pre-amplifiers. The cost of amplifiers is proportional to this parameter.
- Maximum subcarriers (SCs) power difference: this is one of the main P2MP transceiver parameters. With unequal SC power levels in upstream, low-power SCs utilize only

Fig. 1. Horseshoe filterless architecture and its vulnerability against (a) a power outage and a fiber cut and (b) two power outages at the same time.

a portion of the available quantization levels, effectively reducing the usable resolution and effective number of bits (ENOB) for the analog-to-digital converter (ADC). This could degrade the signal-to-noise ratio (OSNR), potentially resulting in significant and unacceptable packet loss. [21], [22].

While minimizing all the goals mentioned above is crucial, they can often conflict. To address this, we significantly modify the optimization framework originally proposed in [1]. These modifications enable us to consider all objectives simultaneously for both fiber directions, which are now interdependent (unlike the previous model). Additionally, the framework incorporates booster/pre-amplifiers for hub nodes, add/drop amplifiers for leaf nodes, and passive 2-by-2 couplers. In the following, we present the model's main input parameters and decision variables.

Input Parameters

- L : List of leaf nodes.
- A : List of fiber links loss.
- G_g : EDFA gain range, 0 implies no amplifier.
- $M_d^{l,a}$: Binary link-path matrix ($|L| \times |A|$) from Hub1 to leaf nodes; 1 if path from Hub1 to leaf l contains link a .
- $M_u^{l,a}$: Binary link-path matrix ($|L| \times |A|$) from leaf nodes to Hub2; 1 if path from leaf l to Hub 2 contains link a .
- $N_d^{l,x}$: Binary node-path matrix ($|L| \times |L|$) from Hub1 to leaf nodes; 1 if path from Hub1 to leaf l passes leaf lx .
- $N_u^{l,x}$: Binary node-path matrix ($|L| \times |L|$) from leaf nodes to Hub2; 1 if path from leaf l to Hub2 passes leaf lx .
- P_l : Launch power per SC.
- P_n : Nonlinearity power threshold per SC.
- P_s : Sensitivity power level.
- P_x : SCs maximum power difference tolerance.
- H_s^p : Add/drop and express losses of coupler s .

Decision Variables

- $\Delta_{l,t}^s$: Binary variable for coupler selection; 1 if coupler s is selected for leaf l at direction t , 0 otherwise.
- $\gamma_{l,t}^p$: Loss of port p of coupler in leaf l in direction t .
- $\mu_{a,g}^{12}$: Binary variable; 1 if express amplifier on link a takes gain g for fiber direction Hub1 to Hub2.
- $\mu_{a,g}^{21}$: Binary variable; 1 if the amplifier at the link a takes the gain g for the fiber direction Hub2 to Hub1.
- $\mu_{l,g}^{d1} / \mu_{l,g}^{d2}$: Binary variables; 1 if drop amplifiers at leaf l takes gain g , otherwise 0.
- $\mu_{l,g}^{u1} / \mu_{l,g}^{u2}$: Binary variables; 1 if the add amplifiers at leaf l takes the gain g , otherwise 0.
- μ_g^{b1} / μ_g^{b2} : Binary variables; 1 if the booster amplifier at Hub1/Hub2 l takes the gain g , otherwise 0.
- μ_g^{p1} / μ_g^{p2} : Binary variable; 1 if the pre-amplifier at Hub1/Hub2 l takes the gain g , otherwise 0.
- ϕ_l^{12d} : Leaf l Rx power per SC coming from Hub1.
- ϕ_l^{12u} : Hub2 Rx power per SC coming from leaf l .
- ϕ_l^{21d} : Leaf l Rx power per SC coming from Hub2.
- ϕ_l^{21u} : Hub1 Rx power per SC coming from the leaf l .
- $\epsilon_{11}, \epsilon_{12}$: Lower and upper bounds of variables ϕ_l^{12u} .
- $\epsilon_{21}, \epsilon_{22}$: Lower and upper bounds of variables ϕ_l^{21u} .
- n_l : 1 if leaf l has at least one express amplifier, else 0.

Equation 1 expresses the objective function of the ILP model and consists of three terms.

$$z = w_1 N_s + N_t + w_2 [\epsilon_{12} - \epsilon_{11} + \epsilon_{22} - \epsilon_{21}] \quad (1)$$

where w_1 and w_2 are weight factors that control the priority of each goal. $N_s = \sum_l n_l$ is the number of amplification sites while $N_t = \sum_a \sum_{g \neq 1} (\mu_{a,g}^{12} + \mu_{a,g}^{21}) G_g + \sum_l \sum_{g, g \neq 1} (\mu_{l,g}^{d1} + \mu_{l,g}^{d2} + \mu_{l,g}^{u1} + \mu_{l,g}^{u2} + \mu_g^{p1} + \mu_g^{p2} + \mu_g^{b1} + \mu_g^{b2}) G_g$ is the total number of amplifiers. The third term of the objective function is the summation of SCs power difference at the hubs' receivers, subject to the constraints described below.

$$\sum_g \mu_{XX}^{YY} = 1, \quad \forall a \in A \text{ or } l \in L \quad (2)$$

Constraints (2) select an index for the gain of all amplifiers in the network (XX and YY have to be replaced with appropriate indices for each set of amplifiers).

$$\sum_s \Delta_{l,t}^s = 1 \quad \forall l \in L, t \in \{12, 21\} \quad (3)$$

$$\gamma_{l,t}^p = \sum_s \Delta_{l,t}^s \times H_s^p \quad \forall l, t, p \in \{add/drop, exp\} \quad (4)$$

Constraints (3) are used to choose the couplers types at each leaf node. Accordingly, constraints (4) assign the resulting loss to each port of the couplers.

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_l^{12d} = & -\gamma_{l,12}^{add/drop} - \sum_a A_a M_d^{l,a} - \sum_{lx} \gamma_{lx,12}^{exp} N_d^{l,lx} + P_l \\ & + \sum_g (\mu_{l,g}^{d1} + \mu_g^{b1}) G_g + \sum_a \sum_g \mu_{a,g}^{12} G_g M_d^{l,a} \quad \forall l \in L \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_l^{12u} = & -\gamma_{l,12}^{add/drop} - \sum_a A_a M_u^{l,a} - \sum_{lx} \gamma_{lx,12}^{exp} N_u^{l,lx} + P_l \\ & + \sum_g (\mu_{l,g}^{u1} + \mu_g^{p2}) G_g + \sum_a \sum_g \mu_{a,g}^{12} G_g M_u^{l,a} \quad \forall l \in L \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_l^{21d} = & -\gamma_{l,21}^{add/drop} - \sum_a A_a M_u^{l,a} - \sum_{lx} \gamma_{lx,21}^{exp} N_u^{l,lx} + P_l \\ & + \sum_g (\mu_{l,g}^{d2} + \mu_g^{b2}) G_g + \sum_a \sum_g \mu_{a,g}^{21} G_g M_u^{l,a} \quad \forall l \in L \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_l^{21u} = & -\gamma_{l,21}^{add/drop} - \sum_a A_a M_d^{l,a} - \sum_{lx} \gamma_{lx,21}^{exp} N_d^{l,lx} + P_l \\ & + \sum_g (\mu_{l,g}^{u2} + \mu_g^{p1}) G_g + \sum_a \sum_g \mu_{a,g}^{21} G_g M_d^{l,a} \quad \forall l \in L \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Constraints (5) to (8) calculate the power received by the leaf nodes originating from Hub1, by Hub2, by the leaf nodes originating from Hub2, and by Hub1, respectively.

$$\phi_l^{XX} \geq P_s, \quad \forall l \in L, \quad (9)$$

The series of constraints listed in (9) ensure that the received power is greater than the transceiver's sensitivity.

$$\epsilon_{11} \geq \phi_l^{12u}, \quad \epsilon_{12} \leq \phi_l^{12u}, \quad \epsilon_{21} \geq \phi_l^{21u}, \quad \epsilon_{22} \leq \phi_l^{21u}, \quad (10)$$

$$\epsilon_{11} - \epsilon_{12} \leq P_x, \quad \epsilon_{21} - \epsilon_{22} \leq P_x, \quad (11)$$

The lower and upper bounds of the power levels received by transceivers in Hub1 and Hub2 are determined by constraints (10). Constraint (11) ensures that the difference between the highest and lowest SCs power levels (this value is called SCs power difference in the rest of the paper) does not exceed the threshold defined for each transceiver located at the hub nodes. The rest of the constraints are used to guarantee that the power per SC does not exceed the preset nonlinear power threshold in critical points across the horseshoe.

$$\begin{aligned} & - \sum_a A_a M_d^{l,a} - \sum_{lx} \gamma_{lx,12}^{exp} N_d^{l,lx} - \gamma_{l,12}^{exp} + P_l + \\ & \sum_g \mu_g^{b1} G_g + \sum_a \sum_g \mu_{a,g}^{12} G_g M_d^{l,a} \leq P_n \quad \forall l \in L \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & - \sum_a A_a M_u^{l,a} - \sum_{lx} \gamma_{lx,21}^{exp} N_u^{l,lx} - \gamma_{l,21}^{exp} + P_l + \\ & \sum_g \mu_g^{b2} G_g + \sum_a \sum_g \mu_{a,g}^{21} G_g M_u^{l,a} \leq P_n \quad \forall l \in L \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

By ensuring that the amplifier output power at the start of the main horseshoe links adheres to the predefined nonlinearity power threshold for downstream signals, constraints (12) and (13) protect against exceeding this threshold.

$$\begin{aligned} & P_l + \sum_g \mu_{l_n,g}^{u1} G_g + \sum_{a,g} \mu_{a,g}^{12} G_g (M_u^{l_n,a} - M_u^{l_m,a}) \\ & - \sum_a A_a (M_u^{l_n,a} - M_u^{l_m,a}) - \sum_{lx} \gamma_{lx,12}^{exp} (N_u^{l_n,lx} - N_u^{l_m,lx}) - \\ & T_{62}^{ln} \leq P_n \quad \forall l_m \in L, l_n \in L, l_m \geq l_n \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & P_l + \sum_g \mu_{l_n,g}^{u2} G_g + \sum_{a,g} \mu_{a,g}^{12} G_g (M_d^{l_n,a} - M_d^{l_m,a}) \\ & - \sum_a A_a (M_d^{l_n,a} - M_d^{l_m,a}) - \sum_{lx} \gamma_{lx,21}^{exp} (N_d^{l_n,lx} - N_d^{l_m,lx}) - \\ & T_{63}^{ln} \leq P_n \quad \forall l_m \in L, l_n \in L, l_m \geq l_n \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Constraints (14) and (15) ensure that the output power of each SC after each leaf node on the horseshoe remains within the limits established by the nonlinearity power threshold for upstream signals.

$$\sum_g \mu_g^{b1} G(g) + P_l \leq P_n \quad \sum_g \mu_g^{b2} G(g) + P_l \leq P_n \quad (16)$$

Constraints (16) make sure that the output power booster amplifiers remain within the linear regime.

$$Mn_l \geq \sum_{l=1}^{|L|} \sum_g \mu_{l,g}^{12} G_g + \sum_{l=2}^{|L|+1} \sum_g \mu_{l,g}^{21} G_g \quad \forall l \in L \quad (17)$$

Constraint (17) calculates the number of express amplification sites using binary variables n_l and a large number M .

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our optimization framework models horseshoe topologies subject to specific network parameters and constraints. In this work, transceivers utilize dual-polarization 16-QAM modulation format, which requires a minimum receiver input power of -22 dBm per SC. The launch power is set at the maximum allowable value of -12 dBm per SC for all transceivers. To minimize nonlinear interference, a threshold of -8 dBm per SC is used to upper-bound the fiber launch power. The network utilizes single-mode fibers with a loss coefficient of 0.25 dB/km. A 0.7 dB excess loss is considered on top of the splitting loss for the considered couplers. The SCs power difference at the hub receivers must not exceed $P_x = 8$ dB. The

Fig. 2. Optimized average number of express amplification sites, express amplifiers, and total amplifiers (and their 90% confidence intervals as error bars) for three coupler scenarios when the horseshoes have (a) 4 leaf nodes or (b) 8 leaf nodes and prioritizing minimization of express amplification sites, and the horseshoes have (c) 4 leaf nodes, and (d) 8 leaf nodes and minimization of total amplifiers first.

minimum and maximum amplifier gain are 10 dB and 20 dB, respectively, with 1 dB increments. It is important to note that a comprehensive analysis of amplifier parameters like OSNR, and minimum input and output power necessitates specific traffic profiles and detailed signal information. However, our proposed model offers a general approach that analyzes the network regardless of the exact traffic profile. This work leverages the statistical properties of real horseshoe topologies from [2] to create 25 synthetic datasets of similar topologies. To assess the variability in our results, we performed Monte Carlo simulations using these topologies. We implemented the optimization framework described in Section III using Julia programming (specifically, the JuMP package) and solved all problem instances using CPLEX solver.

Fig. 2 compares three key parameters: the number of amplification sites, the number of express amplifiers, and the total number of amplifiers. Each value represents the average along with a 90% confidence interval. When minimizing the number of express amplification sites is prioritized ($w_2 \gg 1 \gg w_1$), the average number of amplification sites stays below 2 when considering "70:30 & 90:10" and "All" ("50:50 & 60:40 & 70:30 & 80:20 & 90:10") couplers for both 4-leaf node and 8-leaf node horseshoes (Fig. 2(a)-(b)). Although the number of amplification sites is significantly minimized, the total number of amplifiers is larger, given the need to accommodate the reduced number of express amplifiers. On the other hand, using only balanced "50:50" couplers reduces the degrees of freedom to optimize the solution and leads to the need to have roughly 2.2 and 5 amplifiers for 4-leaf and 8-leaf node horseshoes, respectively. This makes the network vulnerable to double power outages or load shedding occurring at two or more of the leaf nodes that have express amplifiers. Notably, 8-leaf node networks consistently require nearly double the

number of amplifiers compared to 4-leaf node counterparts.

Fig. 2(c) and (d) show the results for the same scenarios when minimizing the total number of amplifiers is prioritized ($1 \gg w_2 \gg w_1$). Notably, the total number of amplifiers is almost halved with "70:30 & 90:10" and "All" coupler sets compared to when minimization of express amplification sites is the priority. However, this benefit comes at a cost: the number of amplification sites more than doubles. Moreover, when using the balanced couplers (i.e., "50:50"), there are smaller differences between enforcing the two optimization strategies, and in all three metrics of interest, more amplifiers or amplification sites are required compared to the other two coupler scenarios. This suggests that the coupler types available for selection can have a visible impact on the solution.

Table I shows the average SCs power difference for transceivers at Hub 1 and Hub 2. All values are below 8 dB, as per constraints (11). As expected, networks with more leaf nodes exhibit a larger SCs power difference. This is because balancing power is more challenging in larger networks with signals that traverse a wider set of diverse paths. Scenario 1 leads to the highest SCs power difference. This is due to the lack of flexibility of the couplers to effectively equalize power. Minimizing the amplification sites also causes a larger power difference. With fewer express amplifiers, there is less ability to fine-tune SCs power balance.

For exemplification purposes, two configurations for a 4-leaf node horseshoe are presented in Fig 3. Fig 3 (a) corresponds to prioritizing the minimization of express amplification sites, resulting in only one being required. Fig 3 (b) prioritizes minimizing the total number of amplifiers, requiring only four amplifiers (a 50% reduction compared to (a)). This configuration sacrifices survivability and becomes entirely vulnerable during a double power outage.

Fig. 3. Optimized configuration of couplers and amplifiers for an instance of 4-leaf node horseshoe for "All" scenario (a) when minimizing amplification sites and (b) minimizing total amplifiers are priority.

TABLE I

AVERAGE SCs POWER DIFFERENCE IN THE HUBS' RECEIVERS FOR DIFFERENT COUPLER SCENARIOS, OBJECTIVE, AND NETWORK SIZES.

Scenario	Express amplification sites priority			
	4 leaf nodes		8 leaf nodes	
	Hub 1	Hub 2	Hub 1	Hub 2
Scenario 1	6.6 dB	6.4 dB	7.3 dB	7.1 dB
Scenario 2	3.8 dB	4.4 dB	6.2 dB	6.0 dB
Scenario 3	4.0 dB	4.0 dB	6.1 dB	6.0 dB
	Total amplifiers priority			
Scenario 1	6.3 dB	6.3 dB	7.2 dB	7.1 dB
Scenario 2	2.0 dB	2.1 dB	2.9 dB	3.8 dB
Scenario 3	2.3 dB	2.7 dB	3.4 dB	4.2 dB

V. CONCLUSIONS

We proposed a power outage/load shedding-resilient filterless metro-aggregation network utilizing DSCM-based P2MP transceivers. An ILP framework was developed to optimize the design for different sizes and configurations. The multi-objective ILP model can prioritize minimizing the number of express amplification sites (representing vulnerability) or the total number of optical amplifiers needed. The results across various scenarios demonstrate the achievable trade-off between vulnerability and cost, particularly for unbalanced coupler configurations. Furthermore, the findings identified a direct correlation between the number of degrees of freedom and the effectiveness of SCs power difference equalization. Future work will involve characterizing the exact network availability using power cut statistics, as well as presenting a Pareto analysis to detail the cost-vulnerability trade-off.

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